

Use of KDP crystal as a Kerr nonlinear medium for compressing PW laser pulses down to 10 fs

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Abstract The input pulse of the laser PEARL with energy of 18 J and pulse duration of about 60 fs was compressed to 10 fs after passage through a 4-mm thick KDP crystal and reflection at two chirped mirrors with sum dispersion -200 fs^2 . The experiments were performed for the B-integral values from 5 to 19 without visible damages of the optical elements, which indicates that small-scale self-focusing is not a significant issue. It was shown that, by virtue of the low dispersion of the group velocity, the KDP crystal has some advantages over silica: a larger pulse compression coefficient, especially at a small value of the B-integral ($B=5\dots 9$), lower absolute values of chirped mirror dispersion, and also a possibility to control the magnitude of nonlinearity and dispersion by changing crystal orientation.

Key words: TFC, CafCA, post-compression, petawatt lasers, self-phase modulation, third-order nonlinearity, small-scale self-focusing

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I. INTRODUCTION

The power and, hence, the focal intensity of petawatt and multipetawatt lasers are currently limited by the size and damage threshold of compressor diffraction gratings [1]. A multifold power enhancement can be achieved using mosaic gratings in the compressor or several parallel CPA channels, each of which ends with a conventional compressor of its own. In these cases, the power of the pulse increases as a result of increasing energy, while its duration remains unchanged. This approach entails a multiple increase in complexity, size, and price. An alternative recently developing approach, within the framework of which power is enhanced due to reduced pulse duration after the compressor, rather than due to energy increase, is free from these drawbacks. This approach has different names/acronyms: TFC (Thin Film Compression) [2], CafCA (Compression after Compressor Approach) [3], or post-compression [4]. The corresponding technique is as follows: pulse spectrum is broadened as a result of self-phase modulation (SPM) during propagation in a medium with Kerr nonlinearity and is then compressed due to reflection from chirped mirrors (CM) with negative dispersion.

The idea to use cubic nonlinearity for SPM was proposed as early as in 1969 [5]. The compression of a 20-ps pulse by several times was demonstrated in [6]. Later, nonlinear compression was obtained in the femtosecond range in a fiber [7], in hollow waveguides filled with gas [7], and in bulk material bounded in the transverse direction [8]. Despite a huge number of works (see, for example, references in the review paper [3]), pulses were compressed only with mJ energy, and the energy efficiency was less than 50%. In the recent years, quite a few experimental results were obtained [9-16], in which CafCA was successfully implemented for pulses with an energy of 1-18 J and energy efficiency close to 100%. An important impetus for

these studies was the proposed and experimentally confirmed method of suppressing small-scale self-focusing [17, 18], even at large values of the B-integral

$$B=(2\pi/\lambda_0)Ln_2I_{in} \quad , \quad (1)$$

where n_2 and L are, respectively, the nonlinear index of refraction and the thickness of the nonlinear medium, $\lambda_0=2\pi c/\omega_0$ is the central wavelength in vacuum, and I_{in} is the input peak intensity. In particular, in [16] the experiments were performed for the B-integral values up to 19. Large values of B-integral enable a significant increase of the compression ratio. Also worthy of notice is the demonstration of two-stage compression [19, 20] and the theoretical works on detailed numerical modeling [21-23] and on expanding the capabilities of the technique aimed at simultaneous contrast enhancement [24-28].

In experiments, different materials were used as a nonlinear medium, e.g., glass [9], polyethylene terephthalate [10], but in the majority of works it was silica [11-16]. As shown in [3], a compressed pulse will be shorter at a minimal ratio of the group velocity dispersion k_2 to the nonlinear index of refraction n_2 . A decrease in k_2/n_2 is especially important for large B-integral values at which pulse spectrum is broadened markedly by SPM. Among the materials that can be used for SPM in high-power lasers, silica and BK7 glass have a small value of k_2/n_2 – approximately $1 \text{ fs}^2\text{PW}/\text{mm}^3$ at a wavelength of 910 nm. For many glasses, isotropic and anisotropic crystals k_2/n_2 is in the $1.5\dots 2.5 \text{ fs}^2\text{PW}/\text{mm}^3$ range. An exception is a KDP crystal (ordinary wave), as its dispersion at a wavelength of 910 nm is only $11.3 \text{ fs}^2/\text{mm}$, which is a factor of 2.5 less than that of silica while n_2 , on the contrary, is higher than in silica; for KDP $k_2/n_2=0.25 \text{ fs}^2\text{PW}/\text{mm}^3$.

In the presented work we experimentally studied the compression of an output pulse of the laser PEARL (PEtawatt pARametric Laser [29]) by SMP in a KDP crystal in a wide range of

B-integral values from 5 to 19 and compared the obtained results with the ones using silica [14, 16, 19]

II. FEATURES OF NONLINEAR COMPRESSION WITH THE USE OF KDP

All the aspects of nonlinear compression (spectrum broadening, pulse shortening, and peak intensity increase) were considered in detail in [3] as a function of two key parameters – the B-integral (1) and the dimensionless parameter of nonlinear medium dispersion D

$$D = L \frac{k_2}{T_F^2}, \quad (2)$$

where T_F is the FWHM-duration of the input Fourier-transform-limited (FTL) Gaussian pulse. The parameters B and D characterize nonlinearity and dispersion and have a simple physical meaning: B is the ratio of the medium length L to the nonlinear length (the length at which a nonlinear phase equal to 1 is accumulated) and D is the ratio of L to the dispersion length $L_d = T_F^2/k_2$. The KDP crystal at the wavelength $\lambda=910$ nm has a very small value of $k_2=11.3$ fs²/mm. Hereinafter, we use the Sellmeier equation from [30]. Moreover, k_2 reduces with growing λ and at $\lambda=985$ nm changes its sign. Consequently, not only group velocity dispersion k_2 but also the next, third-order dispersion (TOD) should be taken into account. For silica, the value of k_2 is much higher (28 fs²/mm). However, as will be show below, at large B values TOD impact is still more significant.

With allowance for TOD, the laser pulse propagation in a medium with Kerr nonlinearity is described by the equation

$$\frac{\partial a}{\partial z} - \frac{i \cdot D}{2} \frac{\partial^2 a}{\partial h^2} + \frac{T}{6} \frac{\partial^3 a}{\partial h^3} = -iB \left(|a|^2 \cdot a - \frac{2 \cdot i}{p \cdot N} \frac{\partial}{\partial h} \left(|a|^2 \cdot a \right) \right), \quad (3)$$

where $\xi=z/L$, z is the longitudinal coordinate, L is the thickness of the plate, $\eta=(t-z/u)/T_F$,

$\frac{1}{u} = \frac{\partial k(\omega)}{\partial \omega} \Big|_{\omega=\omega_0}$, $a=A/A_{10}$ is the complex amplitude of the field normalized to the value at the

input boundary (A_{10}), $T=Lk_3/T_F^3$ is the dimensionless parameter TOD, $k_3 = \frac{1}{2k_0} \frac{\partial^3 k(\omega)}{\partial \omega^3} \Big|_{\omega=\omega_0}$,

$k(\omega)=n(\omega)\omega/c$ is the wave vector, $k_0=k(\omega_0)$, $N=T_F/\tau$, and $\tau =2\pi/\omega_0$ is the period of the optical field. Let at the input of the nonlinear medium there be a Gaussian FTL pulse

$$a(t, z = 0) = e^{-2\ln(2) \frac{t^2}{T_F^2}} \quad (4)$$

Chirped mirrors introduce a quadratic spectral phase, thereby the field amplitude of the output (compressed) pulse a_{out} is defined by

$$a_{out}(t) = F^{-1} \left(e^{-\frac{i\alpha \cdot \omega^2}{2}} \cdot F(a(t, z = L)) \right) \quad (5)$$

where $\Omega=\omega-\omega_0$, α is the parameter of CM dispersion, and F and F^{-1} are the direct and inverse Fourier-transforms. The quantity α_{opt} designates the value of α at which the compressed pulse intensity I_{out} is maximal, hence, the intensity increase factor $F_i=I_{out}/I_{in}$ is maximal too. The numerical modeling (3-5) was performed for KDP and silica with the parameters given in Table 1. Values of B were varied from 0 to 20 by changing the input pulse intensity I_{in} . $B=10$ corresponds to an intensity of 0.79 TW/cm² for KDP and 1.18 TW/cm² for silica. Curves for $\alpha_{opt}(B)$ are plotted in fig. 1a. The dashed curves for $k_3=0$ are given for comparison. Analogous curves for $F_\tau=\tau_{in}/\tau_0$ and F_i at $\alpha=\alpha_{opt}$ are plotted in fig. 1 b,c.

It is clear from fig. 1a that at large B the allowance for TOD in KDP (in contrast to silica) results in an increase in the absolute value of α_{opt} , which should be taken into consideration when

planning experiments. In addition, with TOD taken into account, both F_τ and F_i become much larger for both KDP and silica. This is quite unexpected. Physically this is explained by the fact that at SPM the pulse acquires not only a positive quadratic spectral phase that is compensated by the negative quadratic dispersion of CMs, but also a negative cubic spectral phase that is partially compensated by the positive cubic dispersion of the medium. As the values of T are identical for KDP and silica (see Table 1), the TOD impact of these media is approximately the same (see fig.1 a-c).

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The schematic diagram of the experiment is shown in fig. 1. After reflection from the last diffraction grating of the compressor, the PEARL laser beam (central wavelength of about 910 nm) with a pulse energy of up to 18 J, a duration of 55-67 fs, and a diameter of 18 cm propagated 2.5 meters in free space for self-filtering [17]. After that, the beam was propagated in a 4-mm thick homemade KDP crystal with angles of optical axes $\theta=\varphi=0$. The output surface had an anti-reflecting coating. We used the reflection from the input uncoated surface to measure the spectrum and the autocorrelation function (ACF) of the input pulse. The measurements were made for a small part of the beam with a diameter of 1 cm. After free propagation over a distance of 6 m, the beam was reflected from CMs with a diameter of 20 cm manufactured by UltraFast Innovations GmbH (reflection coefficient >99%, bandwidth >200 nm). We used mirrors with sum dispersion $\alpha=-100 \text{ fs}^2$, -200 fs^2 , and -250 fs^2 . Besides, in the experiments with $\alpha=-200 \text{ fs}^2$ and -250 fs^2 we placed a 1-mm thick silica plate before the autocorrelator to introduce additional dispersion $\alpha=+28 \text{ fs}^2$, which is equivalent to the sum CMs dispersion $\alpha=-172 \text{ fs}^2$ and -222 fs^2 , respectively.

To measure the parameters of the output (compressed) pulse, a glass wedge (GW) with an aperture of 1x2 cm and a mat back surface was placed in the beam path. The beam reflected from the first surface of the wedge was directed to the spectrometer and the autocorrelator. The position of the wedge within the beam aperture corresponded to the place where the ACF and the spectrum of the input beam were measured, which made it possible to measure the characteristics of the input and output pulses in a single shot. We used 1.42 as a decorrelation factor to calculate the pulse duration from the autocorrelation function.

Typical measurement results are presented in fig. 3 for two shots at $\alpha = -200 \text{ fs}^2$. The output pulse spectra have characteristic narrow peaks arising because the input pulses are not FTL, see [23] for details. Note that the measured output pulse spectrum is bounded at the longwave side by the spectrometer bandwidth (1030 nm).

An optimal value of CMs dispersion α_{opt} depends on B (see fig. 1a). The curves for the minimal duration of a compressed pulse τ_{out} as a function of α for two ranges $B=5\dots 9$ and $B=11\dots 19$ are plotted in fig. 4. Analogous curves for 5-mm thick and 3-mm thick silica [14, 19] are also presented in this figure. Note that these are qualitative data, as a different number of shots was made for different values of α . Nevertheless, some conclusions follow from fig. 4. First, the value of α_{opt} decreases with a decrease in the parameter D : α_{opt} is maximal for 5-mm thick silica ($D=0.037$ at $\tau_{\text{in}}=61 \text{ fs}$) and minimal for KDP ($D=0.01$ at $\tau_{\text{in}}=61 \text{ fs}$). The difference is not very large for large values of B , but is significant for small B . This fully agrees with fig. 1a. Second, the absolute values of α_{opt} obtained experimentally are larger than those predicted theoretically (see fig. 1 a). The reason is that the pulse used in experiments was not an FTL one. The absolute value of α_{opt} for such pulses is much larger than for FTL, which was first noticed in

[10]. To illustrate this fact we presented in fig. 1a an $\alpha_{\text{opt}}(B)$ curve for a KDP crystal for the case when the input pulse has the spectrum and ACF shown in fig. 3a: the dotted blue curve is lower than the solid curve. Third, from the viewpoint of minimal pulse duration, KDP, although slightly, is preferable to silica: 10 fs vs 11 fs at large values of B and 13 fs vs 16 fs at small B . This also agrees with the results of numerical modeling (see fig. 1).

The experimental data for $\tau_{\text{in}}=55\dots67$ fs obtained at $\alpha=-200$ fs² are presented in fig. 5. The peak power P_{out} for a compressed pulse with $\tau_{\text{out}}=10$ fs was 1.5 PW (we took into account the 20% losses associated with a lower intensity at the beam periphery and the respective larger τ_{out}). Despite the spread in the values in fig. 5, we can claim that at $\alpha=-200$ fs² there exists an optimal value of the B-integral (on the order of 15) at which τ_{out} is minimal and F_{τ} is maximal. With a further increase in B , the input pulse spectrum is broadened but, despite this fact, τ_{out} increases as $|\alpha_{\text{opt}}|$ is already less than 200 fs², i.e. CMs have redundant dispersion, as a result of which the output pulse is negatively chirped. At the same time, fig. 5 demonstrates that in a wide range of B-integral values from 11 to 19, for the same CMs set ($\alpha=-200$ fs²), all the shots are within the interval of τ_{out} from 9.3 fs to 13.6 fs and F_{τ} from 4.6 to 7. From the practical point of view, this spread is not very large and can be made even less if the input pulse has more stable duration and spectral phase.

Despite the huge values of the B-integral, no damage was observed either in KDP or in CMs, i.e. small-scale self-focusing was not a significant issue. One of the reasons for this is a significant shift of the maximum of the increment of self-focusing instability to the region of

high spatial frequencies, which results in a reduced noise power in the region of the maximal increment due to a decrease in the spectral density of the noise [31] and beam self-filtering at free propagation [17, 18, 31, 32]. Another possible reason is the convective nature of the self-focusing instability at pulse duration commensurate with 10 field periods [33, 34]. The suppression of small-scale self-focusing is discussed in more detail in [3].

Note that further power scaling may be limited by damage threshold which strongly depends on the polishing and coating quality. Being a water-soluble crystal, KDP requires more efforts for both polishing and coating compared to silica. Also, there could be crystal degradation effects on a longer term. This could limit the use of KDP in high peak power fs lasers with high repetition rate.

Thus, we have experimentally demonstrated that KDP can give results not worse ($\tau_{\text{in}}/\tau_{\text{out}} > 6$), and even a little better ($\tau_{\text{out}} = 10$ fs) than those we have recently obtained with silica [16], with the superiority of KDP being still more pronounced for small B-integrals ($B = 5 \dots 9$) (see fig. 4). In addition, KDP has a number of other advantages. First, for KDP the α_{opt} values are smaller (figs. 1 a and 4). This allows a smaller number of mirrors to be used or the same number of mirrors but with lower dispersion, which are easier to produce. Second, for KDP the value of α_{opt} changes less with the variation of the B-integral (fig. 4). This makes it possible to use one set of CMs for a wide range of intensities, as demonstrated in fig. 5. Third, KDP anisotropy enables controlling linear and nonlinear properties of the material by choosing crystal orientation that is determined by the angles θ and φ . Like in any uniaxial crystal, the linear refractive index (and, hence, k_2 and k_3) of an ordinary wave depends neither on θ nor on φ . However, similarly to any tetragonal crystal of $\bar{4}22$ symmetry, n_2 does not depend on θ , but is dependent on φ [35], and n_2 maxima and minima are, respectively, at $\varphi = 0 + \pi m/2$ and $\varphi = \pi/4 + \pi m/2$ (m is the integer). Thus, for

example, by rotating a z-cut crystal ($\theta=0$) around the z axis it is possible to continuously change the B-integral by about a factor of 1.5: $n_2(\theta=0, \varphi=0)=4.6 \times 10^{-16} \text{cm}^2/\text{W}$, and $n_2(\theta=0, \varphi=\pi/4)=3.3 \times 10^{-16} \text{cm}^2/\text{W}$ [36]. Still more opportunities are provided by an extraordinary wave for which k_2 and k_3 depend on θ , and n_2 depends on both, θ and φ . The $n_2(\theta, \varphi)$ function can be found in [35]. The functions $k_2(\theta)$ and $k_3(\theta)$ can be readily obtained from the known expression for $n_e(\theta)$ and from the Sellmeier equations [30]. Thus, for an extraordinary wave, dispersion and nonlinearity can be controlled independently by varying θ and φ , respectively. Note that it is also possible to use a KDP crystal isomorph – a DKDP crystal whose dispersion strongly differs from KDP dispersion [37]. The optimization of the parameters k_2 , k_3 , and n_2 will be considered in a separate paper.

CONCLUSION

In our studies of the nonlinear compression of high-power laser pulses (TFC, CafCA, post-compression) after SPM in a KDP crystal we have obtained the pulse compression factor $\tau_{\text{in}}/\tau_{\text{out}} > 6$ with the compressed pulse duration $\tau_{\text{out}} = 10$ fs, which corresponds to a peak power of 1.5 PW. To the best of our knowledge, 10 fs is the shortest duration of all present-day petawatt lasers worldwide. It is important to note that the experiments were carried out for the B-integral values from 5 to 19, with no damage of the optical elements, which indicates that small-scale self-focusing is insignificant. Analogous results were recently obtained by our team using silica [16]. However, as compared to silica, KDP has several advantages: (i) a larger pulse compression factor $\tau_{\text{in}}/\tau_{\text{out}}$, especially for $B=5\dots 9$; (ii) smaller absolute values of CMs dispersion α_{opt} ; (iii) smaller changes in α_{opt} with the variation of the B-integral; and (iv) a possibility to control both linear and nonlinear properties of the medium by choosing the orientation of the crystal's optical axis and the radiation polarization.

Taking into account the obtained results and the undoubted merits of nonlinear compression (simplicity, low cost, negligible pulse energy losses, and applicability to any high-power laser), we predict further development of this approach toward multi-PW power and single cycle pulse duration simultaneously.

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Figures and tables

Fig.1 Curves for $\alpha_{\text{opt}}(B)$ (a), $F_{\tau}(B)$ (b), and $F_i(B)$ (c) for $\alpha = \alpha_{\text{opt}}$ for KDP (blue) and silica (red): FTL-pulse at $k_3 \neq 0$ (solid curves) and $k_3 = 0$ (dashed curves); non-Gaussian FTL-pulse, the spectrum and ACF of which are presented in fig. 3a (dotted curves).

Fig.2. Schematic of the experiment. CM – chirped mirrors, GW – small-aperture glass wedge, AC – autocorrelators, S – spectrometers.

Fig.3. Measured input (blue) and output (red) spectra and ACF for two typical shots: $B=13$, $\tau_{in}=67$ fs, $\tau_{out}=10.9$ fs (a) and $B=14$, $\tau_{in}=57$ fs, $\tau_{out}=10.1$ fs (b).

Fig.4. Experimental minimal compressed pulse duration τ_{out} for KDP ($L=4$ mm), silica ($L=5$ mm), and silica ($L=3$ mm [14, 19]) for two ranges of B value. The curves are plotted to make the figure more illustrative.

Fig.5. Output pulse duration τ_{out} (blue) and pulse compression factor $F_\tau = \tau_{in}/\tau_{out}$ (red) at $\alpha = -200 \text{ fs}^2$; $\tau_{in} = 55 \dots 67 \text{ fs}$.

Table 1. The parameters of numerical modeling

		KDP	Silica
L	mm	4	5
k_2	fs^2/mm	11.3	27.7
D		0.01	0.037
k_3	fs^3/mm	123.7	106
T		0.0022	0.0023
n_2	10^{-16} cm/W	4.6	2.45
λ_0	nm	910	
T_F	fs	61	
N		20.1	